

THE HISTORY OF EXPLORING MEDICAL TERMINOLOGICAL
SYTSTEM

Kosimova Feruza Khursanali kizi,

Doctoral student of Fergana State University, PhD in philology, Uzbekistan

Kasimova_feruza@mail.ru

Abstract: This article depicts the scientific achievements in the field of study of medical lexicon. A number of researches have been explored and revealed peculiar characteristics of medical terms.

Key words: terms, terminology, names, lexical system, terminological system, founders.

The beginnings of the medical profession were established in the very early stages of human existence and were entrenched in the customs and techniques of treatment and protection from diseases. Medical art has improved along with human society. The slow but steady development of medical knowledge begins in Western Europe in the 12th and 13th centuries. But it was only during the Renaissance that the foundations of scientific medical terminology were laid. The founders of European scientific medicine and medical terminology are Hippocrates, A. Vesalius, W. Harvey and others. The formation of the corpus of English-language medical terminology took place in Great Britain under the significant influence of Latin, Greek and French. The era of the Renaissance and great geographical discoveries contributed to the rapid development of all areas of science, including medicine, which was enriched with the knowledge and achievements of the medical craft of the countries of Asia, Africa, and America. The formation and development of Great Britain as a nation state caused a rethinking of the role of the national language. And although Latin remained the official language of science until the middle of the 19th century, its priority in this area gradually weakened. Further development of medical terminology in English is carried out on a national basis, using autochthonous vocabulary as terms [1]. In the twentieth century in the English-speaking world, this trend received active development, which, of course, could not but affect the state of medical terminology [2]. Significant progress in the field of molecular biology, genetics, radiology, radiobiology, chemotherapy, neurosurgery and other branches of medicine has largely changed traditional ideas about a number of pathological conditions and processes, which has made it possible to take a new approach to the interpretation of the most subtle mechanisms of life. All this has influenced the state

of modern medical terminology, which at the current stage is developing quite quickly and is especially sensitive to external influences. The specialization and differentiation of medical science, the emergence of new medical disciplines, the constant improvement of diagnostic and treatment methods cause the emergence of new scientific concepts, the development and clarification of its conceptual apparatus," while some previously used terms began to fall out of use. Quite deep and detailed coverage in the linguistic literature, which violates the problems of medical terminology, received questions that relate to the structure, specificity of terms borrowed from Greek and Latin languages or created artificially using Greco-Latin term elements , the issue of studying semantic changes: processes of terminology of commonly used words and secondary nomination, the issue of linguistic specificity and linguistic dynamics of certain branches of medicine (pediatrics, pharmacy, ophthalmology, etc.). A significant contribution to linguistics and terminology is theoretical work aimed at a comprehensive study of English-language medical terminology [3], [4]. It is also important to resolve a number of issues related to the problems of unifying terminology, which is used by diagnostic and other devices of different systems, for example, patient – record systems to decision – support systems, unification and standardization of terminologies of individual branches of medicine [5], [6].

To identify the definition of a medical term, it is necessary to determine the limits of the object under study, that is, knowledge of the criteria for assessing the terminology of a linguistic sign from the point of view of modern terminology. The main characteristics of the term, namely its conceptual, semantic, semiotic integrity, are recalled in its numerous definitions [6, p. 118]. Taking into account the above, we consider the medical term as a linguistic sign in the special function of a carrier of information about the system of scientific knowledge and practical activities, united by the goal of diagnosing, treating and preventing diseases, preserving and strengthening the health and performance of people, and prolonging their lives. The scope of use of medical terms is quite diverse (anatomy, physiology, medical biology, therapy, surgery, gynecology, dentistry, oncology, etc.), and the language of medicine is divided into scientific language, the language of practice or clinic, the language of textbooks or reference books, and the language of professional communication. As mentioned above, theoretically, every word can be a term, but it becomes one only through actualization - its removal from the lexical-semantic system of a common literary language and inclusion in the system of terms.

The term is thus an actualized word that marks a special concept in each unit of its actualization. A term in general, and a medical one in particular, is, first of all, a linguistic sign, an element of the communicative system of language, a word.

Based on a thorough analysis of factual material and the study of theoretical sources on the problem of terminology and word formation, it can be noted that the formation of new terms in medicine generally coincides with the main word-formation trends of the lexicon of the literary language, such as borrowing from social and professional jargons, rethinking the meaning of commonly used words (semantic word formation), morphological and morphological-syntactic word formation. However, the ways of replenishing medical terminology also have their own specifics, regulated by the conceptual system of a particular science and predetermined historically and genetically, namely: the creation of terms using only Greco-Latin elements, the use of word-formation means characteristic of the medical terminology system.

Issues related to lexico-semantic phenomena in terminology (polysemy, synonymy, antonymy) can be considered quite ambiguous regarding their solution. Representatives of the normative approach, based on the fact that the term should mark a strictly limited, clearly fixed concept, were inclined to deny the presence of polysemy, synonymy, antonymy, connotation in terminology, or sought to eliminate such phenomena as much as possible. However, the realization that a term is a word in a special function, as well as numerous studies of terminologies and term systems in the field of functioning have shown that terms function in accordance with the laws of natural language.

The unambiguity of a term, sometimes even within the same terminological system, is more an ideal than its real semantic characteristic. How testify results analysis actual material, in within medical scientific terminology polysemy is enough widespread phenomenon, for example, make "cause (death), lead (to lethal result); carry out, carry out (adjustment dosing medicinal drug); make, establish (diagnosis); cause, be cause":

Milder forms of stenosis may be followed until symptoms occur or until the patient develops a sufficiently severe gradient that makes sudden death a risk;

In patients with marked renal impairment, adjustment in penicillin dosage should be made;

Cancer of the prostate tends to spread to the bones, and occasionally the diagnosis is made in the course of investigating progressive back pain;

Tricuspid valve insufficiency also makes the cardiac output determination 18 less accurate by producing artifacts in the thermodilution curve.

Terms that are means of special communication, like words, do not remain identical to themselves over time. They contain within themselves the potential for their change. One of the actualizations of this potency is polysemy, which should be considered not only as a state, but also as a process. That is, we can say that all words

are actually or potentially ambiguous. Terminology is the most dynamic component of the dictionary of any language, and structural- semantic dynamics are observed not only at the level of diachrony, but also in the variation of synchronicity in different communicative situations. Synonymy in the lexical system of a language is a rather controversial issue that has long been in the field of view of linguists. In the modern period, synonymy is considered as an objective linguistic reality, which arises as a result of manifestations of the asymmetry of a linguistic sign and is determined by the commonality of “fields”. As is known, terms tend to have a symmetrical relationship between form and content.

In terminology, scientists most often paid attention to the phenomenon of semantic duplication, for example: spurious (abdominal, asternal) ribs “false ribs”, X – rays and roentgen rays "X-ray radiation". In antonymy, as a designation of the unity of opposites, there are dialectical features of language, which carry within themselves the dialectics of human thinking and, with its help, the dialectics of the surrounding world. Contrasting meanings is one of the excellent properties of language, a clear indication of the systematic nature of vocabulary and terminology in particular, reflecting the results of subject-cognitive, interpretive activity of a person.

In most cases, terminological nomination is a conscious, purposeful creative process. This indicates that both terms and terminological systems as special semiotic models of the theory, in contrast to other fragments of the linguistic picture of the world, are constructed more strictly and rely more on the laws of formal logic. Therefore, among the numerous issues of modern terminology, an important place is occupied by the relationships and interdependence of logical and linguistic factors in the development of term systems. It is very important that the meaning and systemic connections of terms as units of language and professional scientific knowledge also appear in terms of expression (word-formation models, affixes for a particular branch of knowledge, grouping derivatives around a key term, etc.). Thus, terminology, including medical terminology, which is considered as a functional subsystem of the general system of a certain language, is an open subsystem and preserves the laws that are common to the language. A term can be borrowed from a language or an artificially created word that expresses the concept of a specific field of science. As we see, terms and terminological systems are at the intersection of natural and artificial in language, while primarily the linguistic material is natural, and the artificial is the use of this material.

In conclusion, the term is highly informative, logical, has a strict relationship with the corresponding concept, the scope of its use is determined by the boundaries of a certain field of science. The formation of different terminological systems is

directly dependent on extralinguistic factors, namely, the nature of the development and functioning of modern fields of knowledge.

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